

ROLES OF THE MUNICIPALITY OF ISULAN IN THE AGGLOMERATION DEVELOPMENT OF THE ORBITAL HEARTLAND CORRIDOR IN SOCCSKSARGEN REGION

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the roles of the Municipality of Isulan in the Orbital Heartland Corridor's agglomeration development, particularly in the Greater Isulan Area, focusing on centrality and connectivity. It identified missing industries and projected Isulan's future functions based on marketing, administrative, and transportation principles. Surveys from 368 respondents across Sultan Kudarat and South Cotabato revealed that malls, private higher education institutions, and post-harvest facilities are the most lacking industries in Isulan. Respondents view Isulan as a higher-order settlement and key transport hub linking nearby areas to major Mindanao cities, though it has yet to meet cityhood requirements. Statistical analyses found no significant correlation between respondents' domicile and their perceptions of industry gaps; although respondents from Tacurong City had differing views on the roles of Isulan. The study concludes that Isulan will play vital roles in the SOCCSKSARGEN Region, significantly impacting neighboring localities. Recommendations include infrastructure development, policy reforms, and improvements in retail, education, tourism, and healthcare to accelerate growth. High demand for commercial establishments and essential services indicates a promising investment climate. Revising its investment code and its zoning, engaging conglomerates for investment opportunities, formulating a Sustainable Urban Infrastructure Development Master Plan, and relocating government offices to Isulan are likewise recommended. Additionally, policy reforms and realignment of strategies are essential to increase local revenue collection and to strengthen position as the premier economic powerhouse. Finally, a further study is recommended for all identified growth centers in the Orbital

Heartland Corridor, to include factors on climate change adaptation and disaster risk mitigation.

Keywords: *Agglomeration, centrality, connectivity, Isulan, SOCCSKSARGEN, development*

INTRODUCTION

The Municipality of Isulan, a first-class municipality (Department of Finance, 2024) in the Province of Sultan Kudarat, holds a pivotal role in the socioeconomic and spatial development of the SOCCSKSARGEN Region, particularly in the Greater Isulan Area of the Orbital Heartland Corridor. As the capital town and administrative center of the province, Isulan serves as the primary hub for government services, commercial activities, and transportation linkages in the region (Municipal Government of Isulan, 2023). Due to its strategic location, the municipality facilitates economic exchanges among its surrounding areas, such as Bagumbayan, Esperanza, Lambayong, Norala, Santo Niño, Senator Ninoy Aquino, and Tacurong City. Additionally, Isulan functions as a key transit point for people and goods among its adjacent localities and to major cities in Mindanao, such as Cagayan de Oro, Cotabato, Davao, General Santos, Koronadal, Pagadian, and Zamboanga.

Despite its significance in the development of the Province of Sultan Kudarat, Isulan remains a municipality, unlike the neighboring capital towns in adjacent provinces that have transitioned into cities since the late 1990s and early 2000s. Instead, the neighboring Municipality of Tacurong has assumed the role of the agro-industrial and commercial center of Sultan Kudarat following its cityhood in 2000 (Provincial Government of Sultan Kudarat, 2023). Nevertheless, Isulan has not been left behind in growth and development. It has shown robust economic progress, attracting multinational investments and establishing itself as a premier hub for banking, tourism, and the service industry (Municipal Government of Isulan, 2023).

Urbanization and agglomeration play critical roles in shaping the future of regional development. Various national government institutions and private entities have agreed with NEDA Regional Office XI and BrainTrust (2018), which emphasized the importance of centers of agglomeration as key drivers of economic transformation. The National Spatial Strategy (NSS) Framework advocates for strategic urban-rural linkages, enhanced connectivity, and sustainable spatial planning to fully leverage the benefits of urbanization (Corpuz, 2023). In this context, Isulan's role in the agglomeration development of the Orbital Heartland Corridor of the SOCCSKSARGEN Region, particularly in the Greater Isulan Area, should be critically assessed to define its spatial and economic roles in driving development beyond its borders.

The theoretical foundations of this study are anchored in Christaller's (1933) Central Place Theory and Friedmann's (1967) Growth Center Theory. Central Place

Theory explains how settlements and economic activities are spatially distributed (Planning Tank, 2016) while Growth Center Theory posits that development spreads through interconnected settlements and is driven by economies of scale achieved when industries cluster in a specific area (Manalo, 2016). These theories frame the study's exploration of Isulan's functional roles in the agglomeration development of the Greater Isulan Area in the Orbital Heartland Corridor.

Given these considerations, this study aims to identify the industries and services that remain lacking in the municipality and analyze the perceived roles of Isulan in the agglomeration development over the next decade. Understanding these dynamics will provide valuable insights for policymakers in designing spatial strategies, making sound investment decisions, and formulating development policies that will enhance Isulan's position as the new agro-industrial center, premier economic hub, and transportation gateway in the SOCCSKSARGEN Region. Moreover, this study shall provide input in the formulation and updating of sub-national, regional, provincial, and local development plans, land use plans, and spatial development frameworks.

By investigating the economic and spatial significance of the Municipality of Isulan, this research endeavors to contribute to the formulation of data-driven policies that will support its cityhood aspiration and maximize its potentials and contributions into the broader development trajectory of SOCCSKSARGEN Region.

Research Questions

This study identified the perceived roles of Isulan in the agglomeration development of the SOCCSKSARGEN Region, particularly in the Orbital Heartland Corridor and the Greater Isulan Area, based on the assumptions of centrality and connectivity. It also answered the following questions:

1. Where are the places of domicile of the respondents?
2. What are the respondents' perceived industries and services lacking in the Isulan to further advance its development?
3. To what degree is the respondents' perception on the roles of the Municipality of Isulan in the agglomeration development of the Greater Isulan Area in the Orbital Heartland Corridor for the next 10 years, in terms of the following:
 - a. marketing principle;
 - b. administrative principle; and
 - c. transportation principle?
4. To what extent does the Municipality of Isulan compliant to the requirements of cityhood?
5. Is there any significant correlation between the respondents' place of domicile and their perceived industries and services that are still lacking in Isulan?
6. Is there any significant difference between the respondents' place of domicile and their degree of perceived roles of Isulan in the agglomeration development of the Greater Isulan Area in the Orbital Heartland Corridor for the next 10 years?

7. What are the respondents' recommendations for the Municipality of Isulan to further boost its potential for the agglomeration development of the Greater Isulan Area?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a descriptive, exploratory, and correlational research design with a quantitative approach to assess respondents' perceptions and recommendations regarding the role of the Municipality of Isulan in agglomeration development. The research was conducted in the Greater Isulan Area [Figure 1], covering eight areas in the Province of Sultan Kudarat and two areas in the Province of South Cotabato, selected based on proximity and interaction with Isulan. The research was based on the assumptions of concentration and connectivity.

Figure 1. Locale of the Study

Greater Isulan Area refers Northwestern Area of the Orbital Heartland Corridor (*SOCCKSARGEN RSDf 2015-2045, 2020 Update*), which in this study being referred to as the Greater Isulan Area.

The study used quantitative methods for data collection, analysis, and interpretation. Respondents were selected using proportional stratified, purposive, and

heterogeneous sampling. The selected respondents were individuals aged 15 to 69 who were residing, studying, or working in the municipalities of Bagumbayan, Esperanza, Isulan, Lambayong, Norala, Santo Niño, Senator Ninoy Aquino, or in Tacurong City. The minimum age of 15 was set in accordance with Republic Act No. 10742, which grants individuals aged 15 and above the right to vote.

A total of 384 respondents were determined using Raosoft® (with a 5% margin of error and a 95% confidence level) based on the Household Population by Age Group, Sex, Region, Province, and City/Municipality from the Philippine Statistics Authority's (PSA) 2020 Census of Population and Housing (CPH), which reported a population of 366,645 in the Greater Isulan Area within the specified age range. The sample size was proportionally distributed across places of domicile and occupation (i.e., private employee, public official, government employee, student, self-employed, business owner, or job seeker) based on population percentage. However, only 368 respondents participated, achieving a 95.58% response rate. Fowler (2014) contends that a 60%-70% survey response rate is sufficient, and results are deemed reliable and valid. Meanwhile, an 80% response rate is already considered outstanding and indicates a significant engagement of the respondents (Dillman et al., 2014).

Data sources included primary data from surveys and secondary data from government agencies, such as PSA, Land Management Bureau (LMB) of the Department of the Environment and Natural Resources (DENR), and Bureau of Local Government Finance (BLGF) of the Department of Finance (DOF). The survey questionnaire was validated by licensed environmental from the National Economic and Development Authority (NEDA) and the Department of Human Settlements and Urban Development (DHSUD), as well as by academics and research experts from West Visayas State University (WVSU) and Capiz State University (CapSU). The same instrument was subjected to a reliability test using Cronbach's alpha and yielded a value of $\alpha = 0.71$, which is considered good and acceptable (Konting et al., 2009).

After obtaining approval from the concerned local government units (LGUs), the pre-test was conducted for refinement, followed by actual data collection from the respondents. Meanwhile, secondary data from the BLGF, LMB, and DENR Regional Office XII on the average annual generated revenue and land area of the Municipality of Isulan were based on the latest available data (as of 2023).

Statistical analyses involved descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation, and frequency distribution) for sociodemographic data, while Cramér's V was used to examine the relationship between the respondents' places of domicile and their perceived industries and services that are still deemed lacking in the Municipality of Isulan. On the other hand, Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was utilized to determine the significance of the relationship between the respondents' places of domicile and their perceived roles of Isulan in agglomeration development. Additionally, Tukey's HSD test was applied to identify variations among the respondents' perceptions. Cityhood compliance was evaluated against the requirements prescribed by Republic Act No. 7160, as amended by Republic Act No. 9009, and Republic Act No. 11683. The IBM SPSS Statistics version

22 software was used for computations, with a significance level of 0.05. Lastly, content analysis was applied in examining the respondents' recommendations and categorized the same based on their thematic equivalents.

RESULTS

The respondents were from six areas in Sultan Kudarat and two in South Cotabato, which make up the Greater Isulan Area [Table 1]. Most respondents were from Tacurong City (19.02%), followed by Isulan (17.93%), Lambayong (13.86%), Esperanza (13.59%), and Bagumbayan (12.22%). Others were from Norala and Senator Ninoy Aquino (both 8.15%) and Santo Niño (7.07%). This distribution of respondents is consistent with the PSA's 2020 CPH, which shows that Tacurong City has the highest population of individuals aged 15 to 69 in the Greater Isulan Area, while Santo Niño has the lowest.

Table 1. Distribution of Respondents per Area (Places of Domicile)

Area	Respondents (F)	Percentage Equivalent
Bagumbayan	45	12.23%
Esperanza	50	13.59%
Isulan	66	17.93%
Lambayong	51	13.86%
Norala	30	8.15%
Santo Niño	26	7.07%
Sen. Ninoy Aquino	30	8.15%
Tacurong City	70	19.02%
TOTAL	368	100%

Regarding industries and services that are perceived to be lacking in the Municipality of Isulan [Table 2], respondents identified real estate development (malls and lease spaces) as the most needed (26.09%). This was followed by private higher educational institutions (HEIs) with 11.68% and agricultural post-harvest facilities (11.41%). There was also notable demand for government frontline services (9.78%), manufacturing industries (8.42%), and retail outlets such as shopping centers (8.42%). Other essential industries included tertiary healthcare (5.98%), real estate housing (3.80%), specialty hospitals (3.53%), and leisure and entertainment centers (2.72%), tourism facilities (resorts and hotels) with 2.17%, automobile retail and service centers (1.90%), and interconnectivity services and banking and financial institutions (both with 1.63%).

These perceived industries and services essential to the Municipality of Isulan, as identified by the residents of the Greater Isulan Area, support Hidirov and Khudoyarova's (2021) point that agglomeration occurs when a settlement can integrate accumulated functions, becomes the population's focus of attention, and plays a vital role in its surrounding areas. As such, the opportunities to be offered by the identified industries and services are the functions that shall be accumulated in Isulan; and will have an essential impact on its surrounding areas, which, in this case, the localities within the Greater Isulan Area. Moreover, Isulan has already become the focus of attention of the

residents from its surrounding areas as the demand for real estate (shopping malls) emerged as the most common response in the study. Meanwhile, various conglomerates with significant stakes in the industries and services identified as lacking in the Municipality of Isulan may be engaged by the Municipal Government for potential investment opportunities.

Table 2. Respondents' Perceived Industries and Services Lacking in Isulan

Industries	Frequency (F)	% Equivalent
Real Estate (Malls and Other for Lease)	96	26.09%
Private HEIs (Colleges & Universities)	43	11.68%
Agriculture Post-Harvest Facilities	42	11.41%
Government Frontline Services	36	9.78%
Manufacturing Industries (L, M, & H)	31	8.42%
Retail Outlets (including shopping centers)	31	8.42%
Tertiary Level Healthcare Facilities	22	5.98%
Real Estate (Housing)	14	3.80%
Specialty Clinics and Hospitals	13	3.53%
Leisure & Entertainment Centers	10	2.72%
Tourism Facilities (Resorts & Hotels)	8	2.17%
Automobile Retail and Service Centers	7	1.90%
Inter-connectivity Services	6	1.63%
Banking and financial institutions	6	1.63%
Food & beverages (national scale)	2	0.54%
Others	1	0.27%
TOTAL	368	100%

On the degree of the respondents' perception on the roles of the Municipality of Isulan in the agglomeration development [Table 3], the marketing principle reveal that respondents strongly agree that the Municipality of Isulan will play significant roles and functions in agglomeration development, particularly as an economic hub where people from surrounding areas buy, sell, and access services. It is widely regarded as the premier urban center in the Greater Isulan Area of the Orbital Heartland Corridor in the SOCCSKSARGEN Region. This result manifests that the Municipality of Isulan is experiencing a phenomenon of a 'central place', under the marketing principle in the Central Place Theory of Christaller (1933), as cited in Donghoe (2022), which states that the higher-order settlement is serving itself and those lower-order of settlements (van Otten & Bellafiore, 2018).

Regarding administrative principle, respondents agree that Isulan's influence extends beyond its borders, benefiting adjacent communities. This suggests that people from surrounding areas will continue to visit Isulan to purchase goods, trade products, provide and access services, and fulfill other essential daily needs. This finding aligns with Baskin (1966) on the administrative principle of the Central Place Theory, which states that the 'lower-order settlements' should be arranged in a pattern where the higher-order settlement is at the center, serving as the most important place in the area.

Table 3. Degree of the Respondents' Perception on the Roles of the Municipality of Isulan in the Agglomeration Development

Principle	SD	Mean	Interpretation
1. Marketing Principle	0.62	3.29	Strongly Agree
2. Administrative Principle	0.75	3.21	Agree
3. Transportation Principle	0.73	3.29	Strongly Agree
OVERALL	0.70	3.26	Strongly Agree

With respect to transportation principle, the respondents strongly believe that Isulan will become a major transshipment hub, thereby facilitating connectivity between its adjacent localities and key cities in Mindanao. This is consistent with van Otten and Bellafiore's (2018) findings, which contend that, under the transportation principle of Central Place Theory, lower-order settlements lie in a middle way between the next higher-order settlements.

Regarding the municipality's compliance with cityhood requirements [Table 4], Isulan meets the land area criterion with 545.87 km², exceeding the 100 km² threshold. However, its population stands at 97,490 which is below the required 150,000. At the time the study was conducted, BLGF declined to issue an Annual Income Certificate for the Municipality of Isulan, citing DOF Order No. 031-2018, otherwise known as the *Guidelines on the Computation and Certification of Income for the Creation, Conversion, Merger, or Abolition of a Local Government Unit*. According to the said guidelines, the BLGF can only issue the certificate if a bill proposing the creation or conversion to a city has already been filed in Congress. Instead, the BLGF provided the *FY 2023 Statement of Receipts and Expenditures of the Local Government Unit* as a reference for this study. Based on the data, the Municipality of Isulan has a total local source income of PhP 98,074,127.22 at 2018 constant prices.

Table 4. Municipality of Isulan's Compliance with Cityhood Requirements

Category	Results	Findings (based on Criteria)	Interpretation
Generated Revenue	PhP 98,074,127.22*	> PhP 100,000,000.00	For compliance
Land Area	545.87 km ²	< 100 km ²	Compliant
Population	97,490	> 150,000	For compliance

Sources of data (results):

1. Generated Revenue – *based on Total Local Sources Income as indicated in the *FY2023 Statement of Receipts and Expenditures by Local Government Unit*, Bureau of Local Government Finance
2. Population – *2020 Census of Population and Housing*, Philippine Statistics Authority; and
3. Land Area – based on the inputs from Land Management Bureau (*letter dated April 1, 2024*) and DENR Regional Office XII (*letter dated March 8, 2024*).

Note: Section 450 of Republic Act No. 7160, as amended by Republic Act No. 9009 and Republic Act No. 11683. The law provides that satisfying either of the land area or population requirement is already sufficient, provided that the revenue condition is met.

This affirms the study of Pacaco (2017) which concluded that the Municipality of Isulan meets only the land area requirement but has yet to comply with the required

income and population thresholds for cityhood conversion. Despite this, Isulan can still be converted into a city if it meets the income requirement and either of the land area or the population threshold, pursuant to Republic Act No. 11683 which amended the Section 450 of the Local Government Code of 1991. Thus, Isulan only needs to comply with the local revenue requirement given that it already meets the land area criterion.

The study found no significant correlation between respondents' place of domicile and their perceived lacking industries and services in Isulan, as indicated by a Cramér's V p-value of 0.263 [Table 5]. This suggests that, regardless of their place of residence, people recognize the urgent need for these industries and services to be available in Isulan. This aligns with Central Place Theory, which emphasizes the importance of industries and services at the 'central place', benefiting both the area itself and its adjacent communities.

Table 5. Testing of Significant Relationship between Place of Domicile and the Perceived Industries and Services Lacking in Isulan

Paired variables	Cramér's V	p-value	Interpretation
Place of Domicile and Perceived Industries and Services Lacking in Isulan	0.210	0.263	Not significant

*Correlation is significant at 0.05 level of significance

This result confirms the findings of Pernia and Paderanga (1980) which describe the central place as a provider of essential services to its surrounding areas. As such, residents of these areas recognize that certain industries or services remain lacking in the central place. In this study, residents of the Municipality of Isulan and its neighboring communities demonstrate awareness of the goods, commodities, and services that are still lacking and need to be made available in Isulan, which is considered as the central place.

Further, the result also acknowledges the NEDA Regional Office XI and BrainTrust (2018) study asserting that significant and efficient industrial agglomeration growth is necessary for economic development and industrialization. Finally, the result suggests that the emergence of the identified lacking industries and services in the Municipality of Isulan is essential to unlock its full economic potential and reinforce its role in the surrounding localities within the Greater Isulan Area.

On the other hand, a significant difference was observed in how the respondents' places of domicile influence their perceptions on the roles of Isulan in the agglomeration development of the Orbital Heartland Corridor, particularly in the Greater Isulan Area, as indicated by an ANOVA p-value of 0.000 [Table 6].

Table 6. Testing of Significant Difference between Place of Domicile and the Degree of Perceived Roles of Isulan in the Agglomeration Development

Paired variables	ANOVA	p-value	Interpretation
Place of Domicile and Degree of Perceived Roles of Isulan in the Agglomeration Development	0.129	0.000	Significant

*Difference is significant at 0.05 level of significance

While most respondents from the Greater Isulan Area shared a consistent understanding on what roles Isulan shall fulfill, those from Tacurong City held differing views [Table 7]. This divergence may stem from Tacurong’s earlier conversion into a component city in Sultan Kudarat, which may have shaped its residents’ perspectives on the expected roles of Isulan in the agglomeration development within the Greater Isulan Area.

Table 7. Testing of Significant Difference between the Places of Domicile

Central Place	Adjacent Areas	p-value	Interpretation
Isulan	Bagumbayan	0.365	Not significant
	Esperanza	0.184	Not significant
	Lambayong	0.858	Not significant
	Norala	0.737	Not significant
	Santo Niño	0.985	Not significant
	Senator Ninoy Aquino	0.821	Not significant
	Tacurong City	0.000	Significant

*Difference is significant at 0.05 level of significance

For the most part, Isulan is recognized as the central place and growth center, possessing economic dominance and providing linkages to all surrounding areas. Consequently, economies of scale for the entire Greater Isulan Area—comprising Bagumbayan, Esperanza, Isulan, Lambayong, Norala, Santo Niño, Senator Ninoy Aquino, and Tacurong City—are realized when goods and services are concentrated in the Municipality of Isulan. This characterization of Isulan and its role as a growth center in the Greater Isulan Area is consistent with the Growth Center Theory of John Friedmann (1967). Moreover, these findings support Manalo’s (2016) definition of a growth center as an urban space interconnected with other settlements, has economic dominance over the other settlements in the area, and has propulsive characteristics.

Regarding respondents’ recommendations for the Municipality of Isulan [Tables 8, 9, and 10], about 30% emphasized the need to accelerate infrastructure development, improve road networks, expand transport linkages, and enhance digital connectivity. This proves the vital importance of interconnectivity and expanding the linkages of the Municipality of Isulan to the other areas within the Greater Isulan Area. These findings highlight the conclusion of Corpuz (2023), which states that the government must focus on creating network redundancy to ensure spatial connectivity and mobility. Apart from being physically connected, connectivity should also include digital linkages that reinforce

transportation, communication, and logistics (Corpuz, 2023).

Table 8. Recommendations for the Municipality of Isulan (Part 1)

Theme and Statements	Rank	F	% Equivalent
Accelerate Infrastructure Development and Expand Transportation and Market Linkages	1	137	30%
1. Improve road networks (including installation of traffic and street lights)		46	
2. Construction, repair and rehabilitation of roads and bridges		34	
3. Reliable access to utilities and infrastructure		22	
4. Improvement of public market		8	
5. Rehabilitation of the Integrated Public Terminal		8	
6. Disaster risk reduction infrastructure		7	
7. Stable internet connection and digital connectivity		4	
8. Opening of Isulan-Norala-Banga-Koronadal passenger bus route franchise		3	
9. Rehabilitation and Road Widening of Isulan-Bagumbayan-Senator Ninoy Aquino-Kalamansig Road		3	
10. Airport development project		1	
11. Concreting and widening of Isulan-Bagumbayan Road together with the Kalawang III-Biwang Bridge		1	
Strengthen Development Administration and Reforms on Existing Policies and Policy-Making Decisions	2	75	16%
1. Improve/stabilize peace and order situation		17	
2. Sustainable development practices and proper waste disposal		15	
3. Participatory governance and urban planning		11	
4. Unity between and among the people and the leaders of the province and Isulan		11	
5. Progressive leadership		6	
6. Regional Cooperation		5	
7. Tax incentives and tax holidays		5	
8. Foster Public-Private Partnerships (PPP)		4	
9. Effective fiscal management		1	

The 16% stressed policy reforms, including better urban planning, strengthened governance, and public-private partnerships. Similarly, 16% called for the establishment of major shopping malls (e.g., KCC, SM, Gaisano, Robinsons, and NCCC). This indicates that shopping mall companies have a vast market potential and high demand in the Greater Isulan Area. As such, lucrative opportunities await them should they choose to establish malls in the Municipality of Isulan. Around 11% focused on boosting economic development through investment attraction, MSME (micro, small, and medium enterprise) support, and tapping the potential of the BPO (business process outsourcing) industry.

Table 9. Recommendations for the Municipality of Isulan (Part 2)

Theme and Statements	Rank	F	% Equivalent
Intensify the presence of shopping malls	3	72	16%
1. Need malls, shopping centers, and more buildings		30	
2. KCC Mall of Isulan		22	
3. SM City Isulan and SM Savemore Supermarket		9	
4. Gaisano Mall		8	
5. Robinsons Mall and Supermarket		2	

6. NCCC Mall and Supermarket		1	
Invigorate economic development initiatives	4	53	11%
1. Invite investors and businessmen to create more jobs and other livelihood opportunities		39	
2. Promote local industries and MSMEs		13	
3. Need presence of business process outsourcing (BPO) industries		1	
Boost the presence of more government offices offering frontline services	5	42	9%
1. Philippine Statistics Authority [<i>previously known as NSO</i>] Civil Registry Services (CRS) or <i>Serbilis</i> Center outlet		9	
2. Social Security System (SSS)		8	
3. Department of Foreign Affairs (DFA) Consular Office		7	
4. Department of Trade and Industry (DTI)		6	
5. Department of Labor and Employment (DOLE), Overseas Workers Welfare Administration (OWWA) and POEA [<i>now known as the Department of Migrant Workers</i>]		5	
6. Government Service Insurance System (GSIS) Satellite Office		4	
7. Professional Regulation Commission (PRC) Satellite Office		3	
Increase the presence of educational and other capacity-building facilities	6	27	6%
1. Additional schools and universities offering college degrees		12	
2. Investment in Human Capital Development		11	
3. Notre Dame of Isulan College or University		3	
4. Review centers for professional licensure examinations		1	
Revitalize tourism industry and the presence of leisure and entertainment facilities	7	16	3%
1. Promote cultural heritage and tourism parks		11	
2. Cinemas or movie houses		4	
3. Night Life - stores must be open until 8:00PM		1	

Additionally, 9% highlighted the importance of frontline government services in Isulan to improve accessibility for residents. They specifically identified the Philippine Statistics Authority (PSA), Department of Trade and Industry (DTI), Department of Foreign Affairs (DFA), Social Security System (SSS), Department of Labor and Employment (DOLE), Overseas Workers Welfare Administration (OWWA), Department of Migrant Workers (DMW), Government Service Insurance System (GSIS), and Professional Regulation Commission (PRC) as essential government agencies whose frontline services should be available in the municipality. Currently, these government offices are not yet present in Isulan; thus, residents are required to spend time and resources traveling to other cities and access the services of these agencies.

Also, recommended industries that respondents deem necessary to be present in Isulan are tertiary-level educational institutions and professional review centers (6%), tourism and leisure facilities (3%), and tertiary-level private healthcare facilities (2%). Other suggestions, such as strengthening banking and financial services and boosting agricultural support, accounted for the remaining 1% of responses.

Table 10. Recommendations for the Municipality of Isulan (Part 3)

Theme and Statements	Rank	F	% Equivalent
Boost the presence of vital major retail outlets and servicing centers	7	16	3%
1. Citi Hardware		3	
2. McDonald's		3	
3. Car outlets and service centers		3	
4. Octagon Computer Superstore		2	
5. National Bookstore		2	
6. Berovan		1	
7. Rose Pharmacy		1	
8. Toyota Cars Isulan		1	
Increase the presence of tertiary-level private hospitals and specialty health care services centers	8	11	2%
1. More private hospitals with operating rooms		6	
2. Dialysis centers		5	
Intensify the presence of banking and financial institutions	9	6	1%
1. Development Bank of the Philippines (DBP)		1	
2. Security Bank Corporation (Security Bank)		1	
3. Union Bank of the Philippines (UnionBank)		1	
4. Bank of the Philippine Islands (BPI)		1	
5. Asia United Bank (AUB)		1	
6. China Banking Corporation (ChinaBank)		1	
Strengthen Support to Agriculture	10	5	1%
1. Value-addition on agriculture		3	
2. Boost agricultural production		2	
			100%

These recommendations suggest that agglomeration development in the Greater Isulan Area is strongly influenced by the Municipality of Isulan, which serves as the central place and the growth center. Isulan plays a vital role in its surrounding areas, particularly in the municipalities of Bagumbayan, Esperanza, Lambayong, Norala, Santo Niño, Senator Ninoy Aquino, and Tacurong City. As such, residents of the Greater Isulan Area are well aware of the available goods and services, as well as the current and emerging development realities in Isulan. The result confirms the works of Lappo (1974), as quoted by Hidirov and Khudoyarova (2021), which states that when agglomeration occurs, the central settlement integrates accumulated functions, thus becoming the focal point of attraction and playing a vital role in its surrounding areas.

These findings, which emphasize the critical role of the Municipality of Isulan in its surrounding areas, highlight that decision-making regarding its development should extend beyond its territorial boundaries. The propulsive effect of agglomeration and its influence on the localities within the Greater Isulan Area necessitate synergy and collaboration between and among the local governments therein. This aligns with The World Bank Group's (2017) recommendation that local chief executives recognize the importance of coordinating with adjacent and neighboring communities to effectively and efficiently provide core urban services with metropolitan-wide dimensions, such as

transportation planning, traffic management, solid waste and environmental management, and road infrastructure.

DISCUSSION

The findings on the perceived gaps in industries and services within the municipality suggest that Isulan is emerging as an important economic and commercial hub, reinforcing its role as a higher-order settlement. These identified gaps also present investment opportunities, as conglomerates can be tapped to meet the growing demand for malls, commercial establishments, educational institutions, manufacturing, and healthcare facilities.

In terms of its future role, perceptions regarding Isulan's position in the Greater Isulan Area over the next ten (10) years underscore its increasing importance in the development of the broader SOCCSKSARGEN Region. These projected roles highlight Isulan's strategic relevance in the region's growth and development.

On the matter of cityhood, the filing of House Bill No. 11435 in the House of Representatives on February 5, 2025, mandates the BLGF to issue the necessary certification. This development is expected to guide the Municipal Government of Isulan in recalibrating its strategies and enhancing its mechanisms to boost revenue generation and administrative efficiency.

Despite Isulan's status as the capital town and administrative seat of Sultan Kudarat, several key government offices, including the Bureau of Internal Revenue (BIR) Revenue District Office No. 109, PSA CRS (Civil Registry Services) Outlet, branches of SSS, DBP (Development Bank of the Philippines), and the Philippine Crop Insurance Corporation (PCIC), along with the provincial offices of DTI, DOLE, PSA, the Department of Agrarian Reform (DAR), the Department of the Interior and Local Government (DILG), the Cooperative Development Authority (CDA), the Department of Information and Communications Technology (DICT), Department of Science and Technology (DOST), and the Philippine Charity Sweepstakes Office (PCSO), are all located in Tacurong City. Additionally, the district office of the Land Transportation Office (LTO) and the Office of the Provincial Fire Marshal of the Bureau of Fire Protection (BFP) in Sultan Kudarat are also in Tacurong City. Meanwhile, the nearest OWWA, DMW, and PRC offices/branches are located in Koronadal City. Similarly, the nearest GSIS Branch and DFA Consular Office are in General Santos City. These recommendations amplify the intense clamor of the people in the Greater Isulan Area and highlights the persistent demand from residents for more accessible services. Hence, the presence of these agencies in Isulan is essential not only for service delivery and public convenience but also to comply with Presidential Decree No. 341, series of 1973.

In the healthcare sector, although the municipality hosts the Sultan Kudarat Provincial Hospital (SKPH) and several private hospitals, tertiary-level and specialized medical facilities are located in distant urban centers like Cotabato, Davao, Koronadal, and

General Santos. As a result, residents of the Greater Isulan Area who require tertiary-level or specialized medical care must travel to these cities. Therefore, given the growing market demand for healthcare services within the Greater Isulan Area, together with the operationalization of Sultan Kudarat State University (SKSU) School of Medicine, the immediate presence of tertiary-level private hospitals in Isulan is becoming a critical and emerging development necessity.

Furthermore, the findings of this study support the recommendations of Corpuz (2023) on the National Spatial Strategy and Regional and Local Planning for Urban and Regional Development. These include the expansion of interconnectivity and linkages, efficiency in transportation, appropriate policy interventions, enhancement of agglomeration, improvement of services, increase accessibility and productivity, creation of business-friendly environment, address gaps on education and other social services, efficient planning of settlements and production expansions, preservation of protected areas' integrity, reduction of disaster risks of disasters and enhance sustainability, and provision for better governance and quality of public services. In addition, the recommendations of the respondents align with the study of Vargas and Yamada (2023) on the ideal city to live in. In the Philippine context, particularly in the Municipality of Isulan, there is a need to improve the transport system, healthcare, governance, infrastructure, and digital connectivity.

Conclusions

This study concludes that the growth and development of the Municipality of Isulan will significantly influence its neighboring areas in the Northwestern part of the Orbital Heartland Corridor of the SOCCSKSARGEN Region, collectively referred to in this study as the Greater Isulan Area. This area is composed of Bagumbayan, Esperanza, Isulan, Lambayong, Senator Ninoy Aquino, and Tacurong City in the Province of Sultan Kudarat, as well as Norala and Santo Niño in the Province of South Cotabato. Residents of these areas recognize the need for additional industries and services in Isulan, which would also benefit their communities. Among the most urgently needed are shopping malls, private higher educational institutions, agricultural post-harvest facilities, and government frontline services.

Isulan is expected to serve as the central place and growth center in the Greater Isulan Area of the Orbital Heartland Corridor, playing the roles of an economic and trading node, a dominant urban area, and a vital transshipment hub linking its neighboring areas with major cities in Mindanao. Moreover, the Municipal Government of Isulan must enhance its revenue collection mechanisms, through efficient tax collection campaigns and innovative financial strategies, to support its cityhood aspirations and to achieve this goal at the earliest possible time.

Notwithstanding their place of residence, people living in the Greater Isulan Area acknowledge that certain industries and services are still lacking in Isulan, which hinders its development; hence, the first hypothesis was not rejected. Further, respondents recognize the important roles that the Municipality of Isulan will play in relation to their

localities and in the agglomeration development over the next decade. However, respondents from Tacurong City provided distinct answers compared to others; thus, the second hypothesis was rejected. The study highlights the need for improved transportation, infrastructure, policy reforms, commercial establishments, educational institutions, healthcare facilities, and financial services in Isulan.

Therefore, the Greater Isulan Area presents a vast target market with a consistently high demand for goods and services, making it an attractive destination for investors seeking profitable ventures. Consequently, the growing need for commercial establishments, emerging industries, and essential services creates a conducive business environment where enterprises can thrive. As such, investors who choose to invest in the Municipality of Isulan can take advantage of these lucrative opportunities and maximize their profits.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following are recommended:

1. Amendments to both the Local Investment and Incentives Code (LIIC), including the establishment of a municipal investment promotions office, and the Zoning Ordinance (ZO) in order to attract more investors and be able to impose appropriate tax schedules and increase local revenues;
2. Investment dialogues must be made between the Municipal Government of Isulan and key executives of major shopping mall companies and other conglomerates to explore immediate investment opportunities in Isulan;
3. Commissioning a firm which shall formulate the Sustainable Urban Infrastructure Development Master Plan (SUID-MP) for the Municipality of Isulan in order to study the appropriate infrastructures needed towards inter-connectivity, development sustainability, and resiliency;
4. Creation of a technical working group (TWG) to address the identified development gaps by reviewing the existing ordinances that may require revision, ensuring alignment of current plans with provincial, regional, and national priorities, and establishing a comprehensive and stable policy framework to support the immediate attainment of the Municipality of Isulan's vision;
5. Creation of a task force to boost local revenue, attract businesses and residents, and expedite compliance with cityhood conversion through policy reforms and recalibration of strategies in revenue collection;
6. Enactment of an ordinance by the Sangguniang Panlalawigan of the Province of Sultan Kudarat to reinforce the status of the Municipality of Isulan as the provincial capital and administrative seat by mandating all provincial offices/branches of national government agencies, including GOCCs, to relocate in Isulan, in strict compliance with Presidential Decree No. 341, series

of 1973.

To facilitate this transition, the Provincial Government of Sultan Kudarat and the Municipal Government of Isulan shall provide support (i.e. temporary locations, personnel augmentation, etc.) until these offices are fully established.

Additionally, the Sangguniang Bayan of Isulan and the Sangguniang Panlalawigan of Sultan Kudarat shall pass separate resolutions urging members of the House of Representatives from Sultan Kudarat to propose amendments to Republic Act No. 9966, thereby relocating the main campus and the administrative seat of SKSU from Tacurong City to Isulan;

7. To improve inter-connectivity, improvements on the infrastructure and transportation are immediately needed, such as: (a) a request from the municipalities of Bagumbayan, Isulan, Kalamansig, and Senator Ninoy Aquino for the Department of Public Works and Highways (DPWH) to expedite the rehabilitation of the Isulan-Bagumbayan-Senator Ninoy Aquino-Kalamansig-Lebak Road for safety and expand accessibility; (b) a request from the municipal governments of Bagumbayan and Isulan to Yellow Bus Line, Inc. (the only bus company with existing franchise route to serve the area) to initiate operations between Isulan and Bagumbayan; and (c) engagement of the Municipal Government of Isulan with transportation companies to explore services from Isulan to Koronadal City via the Isulan-Norala-Banga-Koronadal City route; and
8. For future research, a study on the functionality of other growth centers in the Orbital Heartland Corridor (e.g., Koronadal City, Surallah, Tacurong City, and Isulan), focusing on their roles, interconnections, and strategies for development, connectivity, and resilience to climate and disaster risks.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This research ensured the highest degree of adherence to and compliance with all ethical considerations in conducting research. The identities of the respondents remained confidential, informed consent was obtained during data collection, and respondents were given fair and equal opportunities to share their views and opinions. Moreover, collected data shall be made available for future research.

In addition, the results were presented to the Provincial Planning and Development Office (PPDO) of the Province of Sultan Kudarat and the Municipal Planning and Development Office (MPDO) of the Municipality of Isulan on March 14, 2025, as part of the research feedback mechanism.

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